

Table 1. Effect of C:N ratio and preflooding on panicle number and rice yield.^a Guangzhou, China, 1988.

C:N ratio	Panicle no.	Dry matter (g/pot)	
		Straw	Panicle
<i>Preflooded 2 wk</i>			
0	31 a	63 b	33
10	28 b	65 ab	29
25	23 c	45 c	29
40	9 d	16 d	3
<i>Preflooded 4 wk</i>			
0	29 ab	72 a	21
10	25 c	63 b	22
25	24 c	51 c	21
40	10 d	16 d	6
<i>Preflooded 6 wk</i>			
0	31 a	67 ab	23
10	27 bc	61 b	23
25	23 c	45 c	28
40	10 d	15 d	10

^aIn a column, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different by DMRT, P = 0.05.

straw yield (Table 1). Significant differences in tiller number and straw yield occurred with C:N ratio treatments (Table 1, 2).

With a C:N ratio of 25, tillers were fewer than those with no added rice straw and with a C:N ratio of 10, but more than those with a C:N ratio of 40.

The panicle number at harvest and straw dry weight were significantly lower with increased C:N ratios (Table 1).

Table 2. Effect of C:N ratio on rice tiller number at 2-15 wk after transplanting.^a Guangzhou, China, 1988.

C:N ratio	Tillers ^b (no.)									
	3	4	5	6	7	9	11	13	15	
0	6.0 a	24.8 a	27.9 a	32.4 a	33.4 a	31.6 a	24.6 a	22.6 a	22.1 a	
10	5.7 a	24.3 a	28.8 a	31.4 a	31.4 a	29.8 a	20.8 b	18.7 b	17.2 b	
25	4.0 b	19.7 b	22.6 b	25.7 b	25.9 b	24.3 b	17.7 c	15.0 c	14.7 c	
40	0.3 c	2.2 c	1.8 c	2.9 c	2.9 c	2.8 c	1.7 d	1.8 d	1.9 d	

^aIn a column, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different by DMRT, P = 0.05. ^bNo tillers appeared at 2 wk after transplanting.

Crop management

Effect of cultural practice for semideep water rice on yield and net income

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Poor crop stands due to low seeding rates, poor germination under premature flooding, high seedling mortality, and inadequate and untimely fertilizer application result in low productivity of direct seeded rice grown in semideep water.

Effect of cultural practices on yield and net income at Ghagharaghat, U.P., India, 1988 and 1989 wet seasons.

Treatment ^a	Grain yield (t/ha)		Gross income (\$/ha)		Total cost (US\$/ha)	Net income (\$/ha)		Net income/\$ invested	
	1988	1989	1988	1989		1988	1989	1988	1989
FPOF	1.2	1.4	154	178	134	20	44	0.15	0.32
FPWF	1.5	2.0	193	257	162	31	95	0.19	0.58
DSNS	2.4	2.9	309	377	168	141	209	0.84	1.24
DSES	2.8	3.4	360	436	181	179	255	0.99	1.40
DSPI	2.1	2.3	263	292	193	70	99	0.36	0.51
LSD (0.05)	0.5	0.1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

^aFPOF = farmer's practices without fertilizer (direct sown with onset of monsoon) - check. FPWF = farmer's practices with fertilizer (40 kg N + 8.8 kg P/ha) - direct sown at onset of monsoon. DSNS = direct sown with normal seeding rate (100 kg/ha) and 40 kg N + 8.8 kg P/ha in well-prepared field before onset of monsoon. DSES = direct sown with 150 kg seed/ha + 40 kg N + 8.8 kg P/ha in well-prepared field before onset of monsoon. DSPI = dry sowing with 40 kg N + 8.8 kg P/ha and presowing irrigation on 15 May; crop was grown with supplementary irrigation till onset of monsoon.

Panicle dry weight did not differ significantly among C:N 0, 10, and 25 treatments, but was much lower with C:N 40.

Adding large quantities of rice straw appeared to reduce the efficiency of applied N. Preflooding did not change this effect. At C:N ratios above 10, microorganisms and rice plants may compete for available N as organic materials decompose. ■

Effect of seedling age on growth and yield of T. aman rice

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We evaluated growth and yield of 30-, 40-, and 60-d-old seedlings of rice varieties BR11, BR22, BR23, and Nizersail during 1988 T. aman season at BRRI, Joydebpur. Test plots were transplanted 15 Sep.

Tiller and panicle numbers did not differ significantly with seedling age in BR11 and Nizersail (see table). In BR22, seedling age was inversely related to tiller and panicle numbers. With 60-d-old seedlings, BR23 had the lowest tiller number but the most panicles. Grain yield, however, was no higher than at other seedling ages, probably, because late tillers increased competition for nutrients.

All the varieties are photoperiod sensitive so days to flowering and maturity of the different seedlings were similar.

Grain yield was highest with 45-d-old seedlings of BR23.

Transplanting 30- to 60-d-old seedlings had no significant effect on grain yield of BR11, BR22, or Nizersail. These

Effect of seedling age on yield components of T. aman rice varieties.^a BRRRI, Joydebpur, Bangladesh, 1988.

Seedling age (d)	BR11	BR22	BR23	Nizersail
<i>Tillers (no./m²) or 25 DT</i>				
30	205 a	221 a	194a	259 a
45	207 a	150b	180a	279 a
60	187 a	135b	99 b	255 a
<i>Panicles (no./m²) at harvest</i>				
30	216 a	246 a	191 b	308 a
45	238 a	230ab	205 b	308 a
60	219 a	206 b	236 b	310 a
<i>Flowering (DT)</i>				
30	65	56	60	55
45	67	55	58	55
60	67	53	57	53
<i>Duration (DT)</i>				
30	94	87	89	84
45	93	85	88	82
60	93	83	86	81
<i>Grain yield (t/ha)</i>				
30	3.1 a	3.0 a	3.8 a	2.9 a
45	2.5 a	3.1 a	4.1 a	3.2 a
60	2.6 a	3.4 a	2.3 b	2.8 a

^a In a column, means followed by the same letters are not significantly different at the 1% level. DT = days after transplanting.

varieties are recommended for areas where planting 45 d after sowing cannot be guaranteed. ■

Effect of summer plowing on N volatilization and rice yield in sandy loam soils

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Farmers in Thanjavur district think summer plowing results in poor establishment of rice seedlings, loss of soil N (by volatilization), and loss of yield.

We studied the effect of summer plowing on yield in a split-plot design on sandy loam "New Delta" soil of Cauvery Delta. Treatments were four tillage methods and three levels of N (see table).

N volatilization in all plots was monitored for 24 d. Volatilization from summer-plowed plots (141 g/ha per d) was 4 times higher than from conventionally plowed plots (32 g/ha per d).

Seedling establishment and water requirement did not vary appreciably among tillage treatments (see table).

Grain yield averaged over all N treatments was not significantly affected by tillage, but increased as N increased from 100 to 150 kg N/ha. This response was greatest (about 2 t/ha) with summer plowing and no puddling. All treatments

that involved puddling gave similar yields and similar responses to N.

We conclude that when at least 150 kg N/ha is applied, summer plowing (with or without puddling) can be recommended for the sandy loam soils of Cauvery Delta. ■

Effect of tillage on seedling establishment, water requirement, and grain yield of rice. Thanjavur, India.

Tillage method	Seedlings established (no./m ²)	Water requirement (mm)	Grain yield (t/ha) at N level of			Mean yield (t/ha)
			100 kg/ha	125 kg/ha	150 kg/ha	
Conventional puddling (without summer plowing)	62	648	5.5	5.8	6.4	5.9
Summer plowing without puddling	58	634	4.7	5.8	6.7	5.7
Summer plowing with one puddling at planting	64	602	5.2	5.7	6.4	5.8
Summer plowing with two puddlings at planting	60	584	5.5	6.3	6.5	6.1
Mean	-	-	5.2	5.9	6.5	5.9
LSD	N level	-	0.2			
	Between 2 tillage practices at any one level of N		0.5			
	Between 2 levels of N at any one tillage practice		0.5			

Integrated pest management – diseases

Natural infection of rice yellow mottle virus disease (RYMV) on rice in Sierra Leone

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Occurrences of RYMV in Sierra Leone have increased, particularly in the lowlands. We studied the effect of natural infection on rice variety IR65 in our associated mangrove swamp at Rokupr in the northwest.

Pregerminated seeds were sown in 5-m² plots with 20 cm between rows and 10 cm between hills, with three replications.

Effect of RYMV on IR65. Rokupr, Sierra Leone, 1989 wet season.

Hill	Plant height (cm)	Tillers (no./hill)	Panicles (no./hill)	Empty spikelets (%)	Discolored grains (%)	Yield (g/hill)	Yield reduction (%)
Healthy	83.0	9	7	11	17	9.4	
Infected	69.3	13	9	83	87	1.6	82
LSD (0.05)	8.3	3.6	ns	12	8.3	2.7	

Fertilizer was applied at 80-40-40 kg NPK/ha, using urea, single super-phosphate, and muriate of potash. P was applied basally; N and K were applied in three equal splits at early tillering, maximum tillering, and panicle initiation.

Severe mottling and stunting occurred in two plots; the third plot had healthy plants with no apparent symptoms.

We examined 25 hills randomly selected from each plot.

Natural infection by RYMV disease resulted in 17% stunting, 72% increase in spikelet sterility, 66% increase in grain discoloration, and 82% reduction in yield (see table). Viral infection increased tiller production but did not significantly affect number of panicles/hill. ■